

Table 2. Rice cultivars screened for adverse-soil tolerance. IRRI, 1976.

Source	Rice cultivars (no.) screened for					
	Salinity	Alkalinity	Iron toxicity	Organic soils	Zinc deficiency	Phosphorus deficiency
Germ plasm bank	1446	1338	12	0	5918	1134
General breeding program	1020	2397	108	195	850	330
Specific hybrids	2059	676	0	0	0	0
Total	4525	4411	120	195	6768	1464

Four IR4630 and IR4763 lines showed high salt tolerance; IR30, IR32, IR36, and 13 advanced breeding lines had moderate tolerance. IR4227-28-3 and IR4227-104-3 revealed high tolerance for alkalinity and 52 advanced breeding lines showed moderate tolerance. IR20, IR34, BG90-2, and several elite lines tolerated zinc deficiency. IR20, IR29, IR32, and many elite lines from the crosses

IR2031, IR2070, IR2071, and IR2153 manifested tolerance for iron toxicity. IR28, IR29, IR30, IR34, IR1514A-E666, and several IR2061 lines tolerated phosphorus deficiency.

Several IR varieties and many IRRI elite lines with good agronomic characteristics and resistance to diseases and insects showed tolerance to adverse soils even though no conscious effort had been made to achieve it. ❧

of observation. The other originally healthy plants showed disease symptoms after the third or fourth week.

The studies suggest, in addition to stubble burning, the following control measures: (1) control of weeds and volunteer rice, (2) dikes and banks to prevent river overflow onto fields, and (3) clean cultivation and early roguing of diseased plants. ❧

Possible presence of bacterial blight in Latin America

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Bacterial blight had not been previously reported in America. During my visit to rice farms in Panama on 5 and 6 August 1976 and in Ecuador on 10 and 11 August, I observed some rice showing symptoms of the disease, and several weeds with similar symptoms. On 12 August I forwarded a report of my observations to the directors general of the International Center of Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) and the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). What follows is excerpted from the report.

On a rice farm of the Bayano project of the Panama government, CR1113, a variety newly selected from an IRRI line in Costa Rica, was about to flower. Small and large patches of blighted upper leaves, similar to those seen in bacterial blight in the early stage of an epidemic, were seen near edges of the farm. Close examination revealed the characteristic symptoms of the disease. Nearby roadside colonies of a common noxious weed *Manisuris* sp. likewise showed symptoms. Bacterial blight symptoms were also found in patches on a second farm planted to CICA 6. There *Manisuris* sp. and colonies of wild rice *Oryza latifolia* were also infected, some severely. Blighted patches were found on a third farm planted to Nilo 1; nearby *Manisuris* sp. and *O. latifolia* were infected. More disease was found on a seed-multiplication farm for possible new varieties bred locally between IR8 and Nilo 1; a great deal of *Manisuris* sp. nearby was severely infected, as was a weed locally called "Cabezona." A large sage with triangular

Pest management and control DISEASES

Ufra disease spread by water flow

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In Irrawaddy Delta, Burma, ufra disease of rice caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* is associated with lowlands onto which rivers overflow because of tidal action. Field observations showed the following sources of the disease inoculum: (1) the wild rice *Oryza perennis*, growing along banks of waterways, its roots in mud and its tops above water surface; (2) *O. meyeriana*; (3) *Leersia hexandra*; and (4) volunteer rice plants.

On a healthy rice plant grown in a pot with a diseased plant, especially in open air in the rainy season, chlorotic leaves appear in 2 weeks, suggesting that water is the agent of disease spread. The following experiment showed dispersal along currents.

In a 100-m canal, 30 cm wide and 18 cm deep (see figure), water was put in and drained at the rate of about 1 liter/minute. One group of 10 C4-63 rice plants with ufra disease and four groups of healthy plants were placed in the canal at 20-m intervals.

The upstream group of plants remained healthy throughout 10 weeks

Plan of an experiment to test the transmission of ufra disease of rice through paddy water.

pseudostems was infected and another weed, *Bracharia* sp., also was probably infected. In the Chiriqui area 200 miles west of Panama City, rice in six large rice farms did not have bacterial blight, but many colonies of the local common weed *Panicum maximum* showed blight symptoms. If isolation and inoculation experiments confirm the observed symptoms to be those of bacterial blight of rice, the original hosts of the bacterium would appear to be the weed species. Upland rice culture probably has localized the disease; in paddy rice, water is a major agent for dissemination of the bacterium. No bacterial blight was noted on rice on many farms of the Boliche and Samborondon areas of Ecuador, but *P. maximum* grew everywhere and in most places showed symptoms typical of bacterial blight. ❧

Seed-borne infection and ufra disease

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Seth observed *Ditylenchus angustus*, the nematode pathogen of ufra disease, in rice grains. Hashioka sprayed a suspension of nematodes in water onto rice seeds but the seeds did not produce diseased plants.

Studies in Burma showed that heavily infested plants produced very little seed; the panicles contained many unfilled grains. Microscopic examination showed the presence of about 15.4 nematodes in each unfilled "grain" and 5.3 in one mature grain. One mature seed carried too little inoculum to cause disease. However, large numbers of seed grown together resulted in disease when naturally infected seeds were used as the source of inoculum. ❧

Testing some pesticides against ufra disease

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Preliminary tests showed 4 of 47 pesticides were significantly better than a check spraying in increasing the rice

yield in pots infested with the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, which causes ufra disease. The 4 pesticides were compared for effectiveness in further tests.

Ten heavily infested C4-63 rice plants, each in 1-kg soil in a 25-cm-diameter pot with 3 cm of water above the soil, were sprayed 3 times at weekly intervals with each pesticide suspension (33 ml, 0.21% ai.), or 0.07 g a.i. of carbofuran granules was sprinkled on the soil 3 times. One control was included with diseased plants and one with healthy plants. Four weeks after spraying, the average number of fertile tillers per pot for the various treatments were: healthy control, 6; diseased control, sprayed with water, 0; with monocrotophos, 1.8; with phenazine, 2.3; with parathion, 2.4; with carbofuran,

4.6. LSD at the 1% level was 1,702.

In another pot test of varied dosages of carbofuran granules (3% a.i.), the density of nematodes was determined by soaking 1-cm-long shoot sections, counting the nematodes in the soaking water, and calculating the number that would have been found in 1 g of shoot. There were 10 replications. With carbofuran applications of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 g/pot, the numbers of nematodes found were 238.9, 96.0, 84.6, 34.1, 18.4, and 17.7, respectively. L.D. 50, calculated according to Bliss, was found to be 0.9825 g granules per pot. Assuming 1 M kg to be the weight of 1 ha of soil 15 cm deep, L.D. 50 is about 1,000 kg/ha of carbofuran granules.

The pesticides may not be economical for use against ufra disease of rice. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

A new lepidopterous pest of rice

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A hairy, greenish caterpillar about 20 mm long when full grown has been observed attacking rice plants. Unchecked populations can increase rapidly and cause severe defoliation (see figure). The pest was first observed in a screenhouse at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) in December 1975, and later on the IRRI farm. The same insect had been reported damaging rice plants at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in September 1971, and in Pangasinan, Philippines. A. G. Hayes at the British Museum of Natural History identified specimens as near *Rivula atimeta* Swinhoe, 1905.

The adult moth is slightly larger than the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. It is cream colored with a tinge of very light brown at the edge of the forewings. The abdomen of the female is greenish due to the presence of eggs.

Rice plants show defoliation caused by a hairy, greenish caterpillar in IRRI Screenhouse.